

A Comprehensive Comparison of Modulation Methods for MMC Converters

Abraham Marquez¹, Jose I. Leon¹, Sergio Vazquez¹, Leopoldo G. Franquelo^{1,2} and Marcelo Perez³

¹Departamento de Ingeniería Electrónica,
Universidad de Sevilla
Seville, Spain,
amarquez@gte.esi.us.es

²Research Institute of Intelligent
Control and Systems, School of Astronautics,
Harbin Institute of Technology,
Harbin, China,
lgfranquelo@ieee.org

³Departamento de Ingeniería Electrónica,
Universidad Tecnica Federico Santa Maria
Valparaiso, Chile,
marcelo.perez@usm.cl

Abstract—Multilevel power converters are very attractive for medium- and high-voltage applications because they present some advantages compared with the traditional two-level converters. In this way, the multilevel technology is backed by the industry and academia support. Among multilevel converters, the modular multilevel converter (MMC) is very popular because it is well-suited for the high-voltage dc (HVDC) power transmission systems as well as it permits the connection of different nature ac grids. To operate the MMC power converter is required a proper modulation strategy. It can be based on carrier-less or pulse-width modulation (PWM) strategies. In order to determine the optimum modulation technique, several simulations have been performed in order to extract some conclusions related with the power losses and the power converter behavior.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, multilevel power converters have been widely accepted as a mature commercial product by the industry and have experienced a huge development in the last decades [1]. The multilevel technology lets to operate medium- and high-voltage systems with a high quality output voltage.

Among multilevel converter topologies, the modular multilevel converter (MMC) is very popular [2], [3]. The MMC power converter was proposed by Marquardt and Lesnicar at the beginnings on 2000 [4], [5]. MMC topology is composed by two arms connected through two buffer inductances per phase. On the other hand, each arm is composed by dozens, or even hundreds, of power cells connected in series leading to a high-voltage dc-link. Hereinafter a MMC power converter composed by N power cells per arm is denoted in this paper by MMC- N . Traditionally, the basic power cell is based on half-bridge topology, but in fact, in the literature there are several alternatives such as full-bridge, flying capacitor or neutral-point-clamped cells [6], [7].

The MMC is a converter well-suited for the high-voltage dc (HVDC) power transmission systems useful for long distance on-shore connections or sub-marine integration of off-shore wind power systems. The MMC is also a good candidate to interconnect two different ac grids through a high-voltage dc connection or coupling 50/60Hz systems if a MMC back-to-back configuration is chosen. In addition, currently it is well known the grid stability problem due to high penetration of renewable energy and its intermittent nature. In this way, the

Fig. 1: Three-phase MMC power converter composed by N -cells per arm. The basic power cell is performed by half-bridge topology.

MMC topology is suitable to connect an huge amount, by the series connection, of batteries or super-capacitors (or both) directly into the medium- and high-voltage grid to reduce the stability problem.

The MMC power converter presents several advantages such as:

- High quality output waveforms and high efficiency.
- Huge scalability and modularity.
- High redundancy which leads into good fault-tolerant capability reducing the operation costs.

However, the MMC presents several challenges from the hardware and control point of view:

- Complex structure because a huge amount of firing signals have to be managed.
- It is necessary to collect a lot of measurements from voltage and current sensors and hence, every sampling time, there is a massive information exchange [8].

Fig. 2: Detailed diagram of NLC strategy

- It is necessary to take into account the floating capacitor balancing.
- The circulating current must be also considered because it can create extra power losses and the global efficiency can be decreased.

II. MMC MODULATION OPERATION

The MMC power converter operation can be performed applying different modulation strategies addressed in the literature [9]. For MMC topology, the suitable modulation methods can be split off in multilevel carrier-less or carrier-based PWM (CB-PWM) techniques. Among the carrier-less methods, the most usual procedure is the nearest level control (NLC), although there are several NLC modified methods such as the random nearest level or the flat-topped modulation [10], [11]. On the other hand, Level-Shifted PWM (LS-PWM) and Phase-Shifted PWM (PS-PWM) are the most common ones in the CB-PWM methods family.

A. Nearest Level Control (NLC)

The MMC power converter is traditionally operated by the well-known NLC technique because its extremely simple implementation. To understand the NLC strategy, a diagram is presented in Fig. 2. NLC proposes to switch on, or switch off, every sampling time a integer number of power cells directly, in order to generate a voltage similar (but not equal in general) to the desired output reference voltage. Considering Fig. 2, the NLC operation for the MMC topology can be summarized as follows:

- 1) The reference voltage, which is fixed by the outer control loop, is normalized with respect to the global dc-link voltage.
- 2) The number of switched on cells needed to reach the reference voltage is determined by the mathematical round function of the normalized reference voltage.
- 3) The specific cells to be switched on and off are chosen in order to balance properly the floating voltages of the arm power cells. Usually, this voltage balancing algorithm stage is based on a voltage error sorting method. Depending on the instantaneous dc voltage error and the arm current sign, the sorting method chooses the power cells to be switched on/off fulfilling the number of on/off cells determined by the previous stage. That is, the balancing algorithm output (S_i) is composed by a vector that determine the next state for each power cell.

Fig. 3: Detailed diagram of the HPWM strategy

Among the most usual sorting algorithm can be found quick-sort, bubble sort and many others [12], [13].

The outer control loop, NLC and sorting algorithm execution times together with data acquisition time define the maximum sampling frequency to operate the MMC. If this maximum sampling frequency is low the overall system performance will be decreased. However, if the sampling frequency is high, the power losses are increased. In addition, these factors also depend on the number of cells of the MMC. So, there is a clear trade-off between sampling frequency, converter performance and power losses in the MMC.

It has to be noticed that NLC generates an output voltage which does not match exactly the reference voltage. NLC generates a rounded version of the reference voltage each sampling time. This error depends on the sampling frequency and the number of power cells of the MMC. This error leads to a high and spread low-order harmonic content in the output waveforms which is a major drawback. For instance, if a MMC-10 power converter is considered and the normalized reference voltage provided by the outer control loop is 7.4, the round function output will be 7. In this way, in the next sampling time, the number of cells to be switched on is equal to 7 (making an error) and the voltage balancing algorithm selects the corresponding cells to be switched on/off to keep the desired dc voltages.

B. Carrier-Based PWM Modulation for MMC

Taking into account the NLC performance, the use of CB-PWM techniques lets to overcome the output voltage mismatch present in NLC. However, the use of a CB-PWM in the MMC presents several challenges:

- Higher hardware implementation complexity because CB-PWM methods require an individual carrier per power cell.
- The use of a CB-PWM modulation leads to higher losses than NLC because the number of switchings per cell is higher. This phenomenon is critical if a PS-PWM method is considered because in this case all cells are switched twice every carrier period.
- If LS-PWM is chosen to operate a MMC, there is an unequal aging and power distribution among the cells [8].

C. Hybrid PWM Method for MMC

Taking into account the benefits and drawbacks of NLC and CB-PWM aforementioned, it is possible to consider a

Fig. 4: Switching cell pattern comparison between NLC (a) and HPWM (b) when the normalized reference voltage is 3.4 and N is 6.

hybrid modulation technique [14]. It must be understood as trade-off between NLC and CB-PWM techniques. In other words, it is able to combine the medium- or low-switching count per cell of NLC with the error-free output voltage and spectrum properties presented in CB-PWM techniques. This strategy (will be called HPWM) is described in Fig. 3 and works as follows:

- The reference voltage is normalized respect with global dc voltage. Contrary to NLC, the reference voltage is truncated using the floor function and the rest is modulated by an extra available cell using a PWM technique.
- The extra cell that modulates the surplus reference is not always the same power cell. The cell that applies a bipolar PWM is selected in the balancing algorithm according to the capacitor voltage level. This idea is clearly presented in Fig. 4 where a comparison between NLC and HPWM pattern switching has been performed. In Fig. 4 a) is possible to check the cells selected by the balancing algorithm in each sampling time and the error made. In opposite to this, Fig. 4 b) shows how the extra cell selection every sampling time and the error-free in the output voltage as well. The balancing algorithm output consists in a vector S_i with the next power cell states and S_j with the duty cycle for the corresponding extra cell.
- In the lower-arm, the modulation carrier has a 180° offset in order to maintain global active cell number.

It can be noticed that the HPWM technique presents the same drawbacks than CB-PWM because the PWM operated cell needs a carrier. However, this operation can be performed using general purposes input output pins (GPIO) and one timer module. This fact lets to avoid the use of one carrier per cell, and hence, the modulator stage is simplified.

III. SWITCHING RATE REDUCTION METHOD

In both modulation techniques previously presented (NLC and HPWM), the power cell switching rate is critical. The power losses can be high because the balancing algorithm can introduce a high number switching transitions. In order to reduce this phenomenon, it is possible to consider the previous

power cell state. This fact is taken into account using the k_i term which is defined as:

$$k_i = S_{i,n-1} + 1 \quad (1)$$

where $S_{i,n-1}$ represents the i cell state in the previous sampling time, that is, $S_i = 0$ if the i cell was switched-off and $S_i = 1$ in the opposite case. This method is one of many possible strategies to achieve it. The idea to reduce the switching rate per cell consists of re-arranging the available cells giving priority to previous clamped cells which leads to decrease the global switching transitions. Defining $k_i = 1$, the reduction method is deactivated and the traditional NLC and HPWM strategies are obtained.

In the following, the modification to reduce the switching rate has been applied to NLC and HPWM leading to methods called Reduced-NLC (R-NLC) and Reduced-HPWM (R-HPWM), respectively.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

In order to validate the reduced modulation techniques proposed, several simulations have been performed. Each simulation is based on single-phase MMC power converter used as inverter feeding a RL load. The most important passive elements values that form the MMC topology have been included in Table I.

At first, Fig. 5 shows a whole simulation that has been carried out using both reduced modulation techniques (R-NLC and R-HPWM) in order to have a complete vision of its operation. The sampling frequency used is fixed to 4 kHz and the number of power cells per arm is equals to 10. According to Table I, the capacitor voltage desired is 2 kV per each cell because the total DC-link is fixed to 20 kV . In Fig. 5 are shown the most important waveforms. The simulation can be split off in two different parts:

- Until $t = 0.1 \text{ ms}$, the MMC is operated using the R-NLC. As previously discussed and as can be observed in Fig. 5, R-NLC makes a mistake between the reference and the generated voltage due to the use of round function in the modulation scheme. This error also made in the arm voltage generated and as consequence in the total output current. Besides, this fact leads into an unknown offset in the desired output power as well.
- On the other hand, from $t = 0.1 \text{ ms}$ the R-HPWM handles the MMC power converter operation. It is clear that the

TABLE I: Parameters of the MMC system

Parameter	Value
Nominal power (MW)	1
DC-link (kV)	20
Cell DC Capacitance (mF)	2.2
Buffer Inductance (mH)	0.8
Load Inductance (mH)	6
Load Resistance (Ω)	10

Fig. 5: Simulation performed for a MMC-10 power converter using a sampling frequency equal to 4 kHz . Until to 0.1 s the MMC is operated using R-NLC and then is modulated using R-HPWM. The signals represented in the scopes are as follow from top to bottom: a) Output voltage (blue) and reference voltage (red). b) Current provided by the upper (red) and lower (yellow) arm as well as the global output current (blue). c) Voltage generated by the upper (blue) and lower (red) arm. d) Capacitor voltages in the upper arm. e) Capacitor voltages in the lower arm.

output voltage waveform as well as the output current present a higher quality without error.

It can be noticed that the balancing algorithm behavior does not affect to the performance of the R-NLC or the R-HPWM methods because the same capacitor voltage dynamic and ripple can be observed for both modulation techniques.

In what follows, the simulation results have been focused on MMC behavior taking into account the power cell switching count (as an approximation of the total switching losses) as well as the spectrum performance. To bring about these comparisons, several MMC configuration cells have been proposed and each topology has been studied under a wide frequency range. All simulations have been carried out for the modulation techniques addressed in the paper, that is: NLC, R-NLC, HPWM and R-HPWM.

In Fig. 6 a comparison between all methods is presented. The grid-period averaged switching count (rise plus fall) for a whole arm (MMC-10 in Fig. 6a and MMC-20 in Fig. 6c) for each sampling frequency used and every modulation strategy are shown. As was expected, HPWM produces more switching losses than others and the R-NLC is the most efficient modulation method in terms of switching losses at the expense of the mismatch in the output voltage. On the other hand, NLC and R-HPWM present similar switching losses.

Focusing on the voltage spectrum performance, in Fig. 6 are also represented the output voltage THD value (MMC-10 in Fig. 6b and MMC-20 in Fig. 6d), up to harmonic 50^{th} , for all modulation methods presented varying the sampling frequency. It is clear that both hybrid strategies present a much higher performance compared with NLC and R-NLC methods. Another important point to be considered is that the THD value for NLC and R-NLC remains constant even though the sampling frequency is increased. In this way, the harmonic content does not depend on the switching frequency.

In order to make a complete harmonic performance study, in Fig. 7 are plotted the output voltage spectrum up to harmonic 50^{th} , for a sampling frequency equal to 2 kHz (MMC-10 in Fig. 7a and MMC-20 in Fig. 7b) and 4 kHz (MMC-10 in Fig. 7c and MMC-20 in Fig. 7d). It can be observed that both carrier-less (NLC and R-NLC) and both hybrid (HPWM and R-HPWM) techniques match the output voltage spectrum, and hence, the switching reduction strategy present does not affect to the global performance negatively. On the other hand, as was aforementioned, the carrier-less techniques present a low-order and spread harmonic content whereas that the hybrid techniques locates the spectrum energy around the carrier frequency. This fact lets to filter the harmonic spectrum in a simpler way if a hybrid technique is chosen. Besides, the harmonic content presented in NLC and R-NLC is hard-dependent on the number of cells per arm.

Finally, taking into account the good performance of R-NLC and R-HPWM, the comparison will be focused on both reduced modulation strategies. Under this assumption, several simulations have been carried out varying the number of cells per arm in the MMC structure. The grid-period averaged switching count (rise plus fall) for a whole arm using R-NLC and R-HPWM are shown in Fig. 8a and Fig. 8c respectively varying the sampling frequency. It is easy to see that the switching losses produced by R-HPWM are slightly higher than the R-NLC as expected. In order to clarify this fact, Fig. 9 shows the switching count increase using R-HPWM compared with R-NLC.

On the other hand, derived from Fig. 8b and Fig. 8d, it is also true that using R-HPWM the THD value drops abruptly if the switching frequency is higher than 3 kHz whereas in R-NLC it remains constant despite of switching frequency increase.

As a summary and considering all previous results, it is possible to highlight the following conclusions:

- If the number of cells per arm is low, it is preferable to use a hybrid modulation technique if the additional switching

Fig. 6: Comparison for all modulation strategies presented for several sampling frequencies when the MMC-10C (left) or MMC-20C (right) is chosen. a) and c) One grid cycle averaged switching count considering the sum of rising and falling transitions. b) and d) Output voltage THD value to harmonic 50-th.

Fig. 7: Comparison of output voltage spectrum for all modulation strategies presented when the MMC-10C (left) or MMC-20C (right) is chosen. a) and c) The switching frequency is 2 kHz . b) and d) The switching frequency is 4 kHz .

losses are affordable. If the sampling frequency is higher than 3 kHz the THD value drops abruptly, and if the sampling frequency is below of 3 kHz is located around the carrier frequency. In addition, in both scenarios, the use of a hybrid modulation method leads to an output voltage with error-free.

- If the number of cells per arm is high, the R-HPWM presents a slightly better harmonic spectrum performance if a high sampling frequency is used. Otherwise, if the sampling frequency is low (which is normally the case for high-power systems), both modulation techniques present similar THD value, but the R-HPWM is able to locate the harmonic distortion around the carrier frequency facilitating the filtering stage.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The modular multilevel converter (MMC) was traditionally operated by the well-known nearest level control (NLC) due its simplicity. However in last years, some carrier-based tech-

niques and others hybrid-PWM methods have been proposed to operated the MMC in order to improve its performance at the expense of increasing the complexity and the efficiency.

All of them present advantages, and drawbacks, depending on the point of view and it is no clear how to choose the best one. This paper helps to clarify some aspects in order to choose a proper modulation technique depending on the MMC structure (number of power cells) and operational issues such as the switching frequency and the power losses. For that, several simulation have been performed considering a wide range scenarios.

As final conclusion, if it is possible to use a hybrid modulation technique (in terms of slightly higher switching losses and slightly higher hardware complexity point of view) the output voltage error will be eliminated as well as the harmonic spectrum is located around the carrier frequency permitting to filter the output waveforms in a easier and cheapest way. However depending on the number of cells that composes the MMC structure, the extra switching losses

Fig. 8: Comparison between R-NLC (left) and R-HPWM (right) modulation techniques for several sampling frequencies and different MMC power converter configurations. a) and c) One grid cycle averaged switching count considering the sum of rising and falling transitions. b) and d) Output voltage THD value to harmonic 50-th.

Fig. 9: Comparison of switching losses between R-NLC and R-HPWM modulation techniques for several sampling frequencies and different MMC power converter configurations. The switching count using R-HPM is normalized by the switching count using R-NLC.

introduced by using a hybrid modulation method could be non affordable leading to a trade-off between efficiency and converter operation performance.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support provided by the Andalusian Government under the project P11-TIC-7070 and the Spanish Ministry of Education and Science under the project TEC2016-78430-R as well as Fondecyt project 1150921, Advanced Center for Electrical and Electronic Engineering (CONICYT/FB0008) and the Solar Energy Research Center (CONICYT/FONDAP/15110019). Section IV was made possible by NPRP 9-310-2-134 from the Qatar National Research Fund (a member of Qatar Foundation). The statements made herein are solely the responsibility of the authors.

- [2] M. Sleiman, A. A. H. Ali, H. F. Blanchette, K. Al-Haddad, B. Piepenbreier, and H. Kanaan, "A survey on modeling, control, and dc-fault protection of modular multilevel converters for hvdc systems," in *2014*

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Kouro, M. Malinowski, K. Gopakumar, J. Pou, L. G. Franquelo, B. Wu, J. Rodriguez, M. A. Perez, and J. I. Leon, "Recent advances and industrial applications of multilevel converters," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 57, no. 8, pp. 2553–2580, Aug 2010.
- [3] S. Debnath, J. Qin, B. Bahrani, M. Saeedifard, and P. Barbosa, "Operation, control, and applications of the modular multilevel converter: A review," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 30, no. 1, pp. 37–53, Jan 2015.
- [4] A. Lesnicar and R. Marquardt, "An innovative modular multilevel converter topology suitable for a wide power range," in *2003 IEEE Bologna Power Tech Conference Proceedings*, vol. 3, June 2003, pp. 6 pp. Vol.3–.
- [5] K. Sharifabadi, L. Harnefors, H.-P. Nee, S. Norrga, and R. Teodorescu, *Introduction to Modular Multilevel Converters*. Wiley-IEEE Press, 2016, pp. 416–. [Online]. Available: <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/articleDetails.jsp?arnumber=7656919>
- [6] A. Nami, J. Liang, F. Dijkhuizen, and G. D. Demetriades, "Modular multilevel converters for hvdc applications: Review on converter cells and functionalities," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 30, no. 1, pp. 18–36, Jan 2015.
- [7] M. A. Perez, S. Bernet, J. Rodriguez, S. Kouro, and R. Lizana, "Circuit topologies, modeling, control schemes, and applications of modular multilevel converters," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 30, no. 1, pp. 4–17, Jan 2015.
- [8] L. Mathe, P. D. Burlacu, and R. Teodorescu, "Control of a modular multilevel converter with reduced internal data exchange," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 248–257, Feb 2017.
- [9] J. I. Leon, S. Kouro, L. G. Franquelo, J. Rodriguez, and B. Wu, "The essential role and the continuous evolution of modulation techniques for voltage-source inverters in the past, present, and future power electronics," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 63, no. 5, pp. 2688–2701, May 2016.
- [10] C. Qi, P. Tu, P. Wang, and M. A. Zagrodnik, "Random nearest level modulation strategy of multilevel cascaded h-bridge inverters," *IET Power Electronics*, vol. 9, no. 14, pp. 2706–2713, 2016.
- [11] R. Li, J. E. Fletcher, L. Xu, and B. W. Williams, "Enhanced flat-topped modulation for mmc control in hvdc transmission systems," *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 152–161, Feb 2017.
- [12] C. D. Thompson, "The vlsi complexity of sorting," *IEEE Transactions on Computers*, vol. C-32, no. 12, pp. 1171–1184, Dec 1983.
- [13] D. Siemaszko, "Fast sorting method for balancing capacitor voltages in modular multilevel converters," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 30, no. 1, pp. 463–470, Jan 2015.
- [14] S. Rohner, S. Bernet, M. Hiller, and R. Sommer, "Modulation, losses, and semiconductor requirements of modular multilevel converters," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 57, no. 8, pp. 2633–2642, Aug 2010.

IEEE 23rd International Symposium on Industrial Electronics (ISIE), June 2014, pp. 2149–2154.